

IN-HABIT - INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D8.2 PROMOTIONAL VIDEO

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Authors (names and affiliations)	C. Marrone, S. Marrone, D. Bordin, E. Cianchi - Book on a Tree		

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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Status	Date	Contributor/partner	Summary of changes
V 0.1	Draft/	23/09/2021	C. Marrone, S. Marrone, D. Bordin, E. Cianchi (BOT)	Initial drafting
V 0.2	Draft	27/09/2021	C. Marrone, S. Marrone, D. Bordin, E. Cianchi (BOT)	Advanced draft
V 0.3	Advanced draft	29/09/2021	BOT	Language final revision
V 0.4	Final document	30/09/2021	BOT	Revisions included

LIST OF ACRONYMS

D	Deliverable
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication & Outreach
DC	Dissemination & Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union

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GA	Grant Agreement
GDEI	Gender, Diversity, Equity, Inclusion
H2020	Horizon 2020 projects
IHW	Inclusive Health and Wellbeing
KLC	Key Local Contact
LCA	Local Community Activator
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Project Partner
SMSCs	Small and medium-sized cities
T	Task
WP	Work Package

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Deliverable description

This document outlines the development of the INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies (IN-HABIT) promotional video – WP8 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) strategy – deliverable D8.2 of task 8.2 (communication and engagement actions and tools).

The outcome is a promotional video about the project and four local spotlight videos, available at the following link: <https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/media-press/>

Starting from M4, a discussion was opened up with Project Partners to communicate and disseminate the project objectives and to combine the foreseen promotional video with four short local teaser videos, to be used in launch campaigns for local customised dissemination.

This option would allow Key Local Contacts (KLCs) and Local Community Activators (LCAs), along with all the local partners and population involved in the project, to better communicate the cities' highlights and innovations, from a local perspective.

The ultimate goal is to produce dynamic, user-friendly and easy-to-understand content to enhance public awareness and promote local innovations and spaces, through a recognisable and strong visual identity based on the project's communication guidelines. Moreover, given the significance and central position that GDEI approach represents in the overall project and in its communication in this case, particular attention was put into the use of inclusiveness both in language as well as visual content.

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After the confirmation and development of the visual identity of the project in M6, and following a co-design process with the Project Partners (PPs), in particular local ones, the first release of the promotional video took place in M10 for the general video and M11-12 for the local ones. Feedback from Project Partners has been carefully collected and requested amends applied accordingly.

1.2 Technical features

The promotional videos have been created using professional skills and involving professional video makers.

Images were shot in full HD 1920 X 1080 resolution, with the footage representing a good 70% of the videos, and stock footage material used only when necessary.

BOT has relied on local video operators, above all to have a direct connection with the territories and local innovations depicted, and also to enhance the professionalism of the videos.

A professional interpreter has taken care of the voice over, and the right pronunciation of wording in local languages has been carefully reviewed by relying on local contacts.

2. PRODUCTION PROCESS

2.1 Conceptual phase and visuals

The IN-HABIT promotional video has been defined and confirmed, and comprises two parts: general promotional video and local spotlight videos.

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The general aim of the promotional video is to communicate the project identity and convey its core messages through the use of a dynamic, attention-grabbing description of the actions, while at the same time conveying important contextual information through infographics that adhere to the project visual identity and through selected icons, imagery, and 2-D animations. The use of carefully selected imagery helps viewers to better understand the reach of the project and the main actions in a specific, effective way.

The project visual identity has been incorporated in the videos through the use of icons, a distinctive trait of the project’s visuals. The icons allow immediate communication and a friendly, easy-to-use interface.

Infographics and 2D animation have also been utilised in order to include complex information in simpler representations, and to convey project information wherever available. Finally, the result was to offer a friendlier, immediate and dynamic approach.

2.2 Editing and finalising

General and local scripts, along with the accompanying suitable imagery and wording, were carefully written and analysed with corresponding partners.

The script of the **general promotional video** is as follows:

Table 1. General video script

Voiceover	Typography	Imagery
	Inclusive Health and wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies	IN-HABIT logo

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Europe 2030: over 80% of people will live in urban areas	Europe 2030: over 80% of people will live in urban areas	Urban areas
Through urban innovation, IN-HABIT will help	urban innovation	
Foster social and labour inclusion, and inclusive healthy lifestyles through culture and heritage	culture and heritage	Imagery representing culture and heritage
Promote inclusive healthy lifestyles and well-being through food	food	Food-related imagery
Promote inclusive mental health, social and relational well-being through human-animal bonds	human-animal bonds	Imagery showing people with pets
Boost healthy lifestyles, social inclusion of migrants and relational well-being through arts and environment	arts and environment	Imagery representing arts and environment
So... what is urban innovation all about?	what is urban innovation all about?	
Making cities sustainable, safe and inclusive	sustainable safe inclusive	

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IN-HABIT will carry out cutting-edge research to promote inclusive health and well-being in urban spaces	cutting-edge research	
Through a gender, diversity, equity and inclusion perspective	gender, diversity, equity and inclusion perspective	GDEI-related imagery
Co-designing, co-deploying and co-managing visionary and integrated solutions in urban public spaces	co-designing co-deploying co-managing visionary and integrated solutions in urban public spaces	
Cordoba: Culture and heritage hub	Cordoba: Culture and heritage hub	Images of Cordoba with culture icon
Riga: Multifunctional food hub	Riga: Multifunctional food hub	Images of Riga with food icon
Lucca: Human-animal bonds hub	Lucca: Human-animal bonds hub	Images of Lucca with animal icon
Nitra: Art and environment hub	Nitra: Art and environment hub	Images of Nitra with art and environment icon
IN-HABIT will investigate the impact of: cultural, digital and technological, nature based, and social innovations on inhabitants' health and well-being	cultural digital and technological nature based social innovations	
Driving measurable change	driving measurable change	

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Pilots in Cordoba, Lucca, Nitra and Riga will share knowledge to spread inclusive-oriented urban innovation and replicate their experiences in other cities such as Bogota	Cordoba: Culture Lucca: Animals Nitra: Art & environment Riga: Food share knowledge Bogota	Map showing countries and with relevant icons
Urban innovation is your city improved for everyone	urban innovation is your city improved for everyone	
Join the IN-HABIT revolution		
	inhabit-h2020.eu facebook.com/inhabith2020 linkedin.com/company/68868676 twitter.com/INHABIT_H2020	IN-HABIT logo
	THE IN-HABIT PARTNERS	Partner logos

In particular, for the local videos, after an internal discussion with the PPs, English was maintained as the video language for the voiceover, to allow the dissemination of local actions to wider audiences, while subtitles were added and checked in the four local languages of the project (Spanish, Italian, Latvian, Slovak).

The scripts of the **four local videos** are as follows:

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Table 2. Local video scripts

CORDOBA			
Voiceover	Subtitles	Typography	Visuals
		Inclusive Health and wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies	IN-HABIT logo
Cordoba: Culture and heritage hub	Córdoba: Nodo de cultura y patrimonio	Cordoba: Culture and heritage hub	Images of Cordoba with the culture icon
Building on the city's rich cultural heritage	Creando oportunidades a través de nuestra riqueza cultural y patrimonial	rich cultural heritage	Images of Medina Azahara
IN-HABIT will investigate how cultural innovations foster inclusive health and well-being by transforming Las Palmeras central square and courtyards into green, sustainable, creative areas.	IN-HABIT investigará cómo la integración de distintos tipos de innovaciones alrededor de innovaciones culturales pueden incrementar la salud y el bienestar inclusivos y utilizará como pilotos los patios, con especial hincapié en los de Las Palmeras	cultural innovations inclusive health and well-being green, sustainable, creative areas	Images of Las Palmeras squares and courtyards

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Hosting initiatives from culture and heritage to food and leisure, the spaces will facilitate community decision making and drive health and well-being.	Promoverá iniciativas relacionadas con cultura, patrimonio alimentación saludable y ocio, creando espacios que faciliten la toma de decisiones colectivas y que formenten la salud y el bienestar.	culture and heritage food and leisure community decision making health and well-being	Images of the spaces and people coming together
Through culture and heritage, IN-HABIT will foster inclusive healthy lifestyles in Cordoba.	A través de la cultura y el patrimonio, IN-HABIT fomentará estilos de vida saludables e inclusivos en Córdoba.	culture and heritage inclusive healthy lifestyles	Image representing a healthy lifestyle
Join the IN-HABIT transformation	Únete a la transformación IN-HABIT!!	join the IN-HABIT transformation	
		inhabit-h2020.eu cordoba@inhabit-h2020.eu facebook.com/inhabit-h2020 linkedin.com/company/68868676 twitter.com/INHABIT_H2020	IN-HABIT logo
		THE IN-HABIT PARTNERS	Partner logos

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LUCCA			
Voiceover	Subtitles	Typography	Visuals
		Inclusive Health and wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies	IN-HABIT logo
Lucca: Human-animal bonds hub	Lucca: Centro dedicato al rapporto uomo-animale	Lucca: Human-animal bonds hub	Images of Lucca with the animal icon
Building on the city's large population of animals	Basandosi sulla ampia popolazione animale presente nella città	large population of animals	Images of human-animal interactions
IN-HABIT will deploy animal assisted interventions in public spaces, connect different neighbourhoods with dedicated animal lines, and implement pet policies to become Europe's first human-animal smart city.	IN-HABIT svilupperà nei luoghi pubblici interventi assistiti con animali, conetterà quartieri diversi con il percorso delle animabili e implementerà politiche pet friendly per diventare la prima città smart in Europa con un'attenzione al rapporto uomo animale.	animal assisted interventions dedicated animal lines pet policies human-animal smart city	

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Human-animal initiatives will facilitate the inclusion of less empowered individuals and improve social relations and sharing.	Iniziative finalizzate a sviluppare il rapporto uomo-animale faciliteranno l'inclusione di persone vulnerabili e miglioreranno le relazioni sociali e la condivisione.	inclusion of less empowered individuals social relations and sharing	
Through human-animal bonds, IN-HABIT will promote inclusive mental health and social and relational well-being in Lucca.	Attraverso il legame uomo-animale IN-HABIT promuoverà a Lucca salute mentale inclusiva e benessere sociale e relazionale.	human-animal bonds inclusive mental health social and relational well-being	
Join the IN-HABIT transformation	Unisciti alla trasformazione di IN-HABIT	join the IN-HABIT transformation	
		inhabit-h2020.eu lucca@inhabit-h2020.eu facebook.com/inhabith2020 linkedin.com/company/68868676 twitter.com/INHABIT_H2020	IN-HABIT logo
		THE IN-HABIT PARTNERS	Partner logo

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NITRA			
Voiceover	Subtitles	Typography	Visuals
		Inclusive Health and wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies	IN-HABIT logo
Nitra: Art and environment hub	Nitra: Hub umenia a environmentu	Nitra: Art and environment hub	Images of Nitra with the art & environment hub icon
Responding to the need to better integrate diverse communities	Adresuje potrebu lepšej integrácie rozličných komunit	better integrate diverse communities	Image showing diverse communities coming together
IN-HABIT will establish a multifunctional corridor featuring reversible urban mobiliary elements, interactive lighting, experimental gardens, a community kitchen and a DIY workshop.	IN-HABIT vytvorí multifunkčný koridor zahŕňajúci element reverzibilného mobiliáru, interaktívneho osvetlenia experimentálnych záhrad, komunitnej kuchyne, a DIY workshop.	multifunctional corridor reversible urban mobiliary elements interactive lighting experimental gardens community kitchen DIY workshop	Images showing gardens, community kitchens etc.

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Linking two neighbourhoods, the corridor will transform the surrounding area through innovation and foster inclusion with spaces for everyone.	Prepájajúc dve susedstvá, koridor bude transformovať okolitý priestor prostredníctvom inovácií a podporovať inklúziu vďaka priestranstvám pre všetkých.	transform the surrounding area foster inclusion	Images of people coming together in an outdoor space
Through arts and environment, IN-HABIT will boost healthy lifestyles, social inclusion and relational well-being in Nitra.	Prostredníctvom umenia a zlepšeného životného prostredia, IN-HABIT prispeje k zdravému životnému štýlu sociálnej inklúzie a relačnému blahobytu v meste Nitra.	arts and environment healthy lifestyles social inclusion relational well-being	
Join the IN-HABIT transformation	Pridaj sa k transformácií IN-HABIT	join the IN-HABIT transformation	
		inhabit-h2020.eu nitra@inhabit-h2020.eu facebook.com/inhabith2020 0 linkedin.com/company/68868676 twitter.com/INHABIT_H2020 LOCAL SOCIAL MEDIA www.facebook.com/InHubNitra	IN-HABIT logo Email: nitra@inhabit-h2020.eu

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		THE IN-HABIT PARTNERS	Partner logos
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RIGA			
Voiceover	Subtitles	Typography	Visuals
		Inclusive Health and wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies	IN-HABIT logo
Riga: Multifunctional food hub	Rīga: multifunkcionāls partikās centrs	Riga: Multifunctional food hub	Images of Riga with food icon
Building on the success of the recently developed Āgenskalns urban quarter	Turpinot sekmīgi aizsākto Āgenskalna tirgus apkārtnes attīstību	the success Āgenskalns urban quarter	Images of Āgenskalns urban quarter
IN-HABIT will deploy sustainable trade and zero waste initiatives in the Āgelnskans market area including a community kitchen, eco-island and waste-reduction site.	IN-HABIT ietvaros Āgenskalna tirgus teritorijā tiks ieviestas dažādas ilgtspējīgas tirdzniecības un bezatkritumu iniciatīvas, to skaitā kopienas virtuve eko-sala un atkritumu samazināšanas punkts	sustainable trade and zero waste initiatives community kitchen eco island waste-reduction site	Images of the market area

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The redeveloped building and market area will host events and initiatives, providing a community space for gathering and bonding.	Atjaunotajā Āgenskalna tirgus ēkā un tirgus zonā tiks organizēti pasākumi kas kalpos kā kopienas pulcēšanās un tās stiprināšanas vieta.	events and initiatives community space	
Through food, IN-HABIT will promote inclusive healthy lifestyles and well-being in Riga.	Caur ēdienu, IN-HABIT projekts veicinās iekļaujošu veselīgu dzīvesveidu un labklājību Rīgā	food Inclusive healthy lifestyles and well-being	Images of food
Join the IN-HABIT transformation	Pievienojies IN-HABIT veidotajām pārmaiņām	join the IN-HABIT transformation	
		inhabit-h2020.eu riga@inhabit-h2020.eu facebook.com/inhabith2020 linkedin.com/company/68868676 twitter.com/INHABIT_H2020 LOCAL SOCIAL MEDIA www.facebook.com/InHabitRiga	IN-HABIT logo
		THE IN-HABIT PARTNERS	Partner logo

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The general video and the four local, shorter videos all end with a final slide with logos of the organisations and credits.

BOT also included the Bogotá partner on the map in the general video, doing extensive research looking for images or footage of the Transmicable, to give the audience an idea of the broadness of the project innovations.

Given that inclusiveness is one of IN-HABIT's guiding values both in internal and external communication, following a GDEI approach, careful thought was put into the representation of images, taking into account the characteristics and the social/cultural features of different cultures. BOT also ensured that the language used for the communication was accessible to non-experts, avoiding any reference to EU jargon and technical terms. Moreover, GDEI approach and inclusion aspects were introduced in all videos, throughout the use of inclusive language, following the project framework that considers this approach central both in the project's actions and general communication in all channels.

Finally, local social media channels and contact information were shared in order to have a central role in reaching out to groups of categories and collectives at risk of exclusion.

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3. RELEASES

As previously mentioned, the releases have followed a co-design process with the partners, both for the general and local videos. The general promotional video was presented to PPs in M9 and finalised following the requested amends, collected through dedicated meetings and communications, in M10. Improvements to the script and voiceover were included where requested. The local videos were finally finalised in M13, following an accurate review process by the local partners.

Fig. 1 - Screenshot of general promotional video

Fig. 2 - Screenshot of Cordoba local video

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Fig. 3 - Screenshot of Riga local video

Fig. 4 - Screenshot of Lucca local video

Fig. 5 - Screenshot of Nitra local video

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